

CURRENT ISSUES OF LOGISTICS INDUSTRY FINANCING

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Abstract: The article studies the scientific and theoretical aspects of the factors influencing the financial activity of enterprises in the logistics system in the national economy. Also, urgent problems related to improving the practice of financing the logistics industry were identified, and scientific proposals were developed aimed at solving them. The study presents the author's approaches and proposals.

Keywords: Economic system, logistics system, financing, financial performance, econometric modeling, panel data, economic analysis, financial analysis.

Nowadays, in the process of intense competition, enterprises providing logistics services aim to reduce their expenses to a minimum level and increase their income, among others, to increase their economic performance.

Since enterprises in the logistics system participate in several stages of the supply chain, this goal is not only beneficial for them, but also appropriate for other parties in the supply chain.

Material flow in the financing of enterprises in the logistics system is the main type of commercial logistics, which is at the same time the organization of economic matter and its form of movement.

In analyzing the financial activity of logistics enterprises, the sources of financial resources formation, its structural structure, the dynamic state of assets, and the influence of endogenous and exogenous factors are studied.

Today, the logistics sector is even more important when considered as the basis for economic sectors, because it helps to connect the flow of services and goods from the first partners to the final customers.

The logistics sector is the backbone of the national economy and is considered the driving force of all branches of agriculture, production or service.

Today, the need to more accurately forecast the market situation and the company's position in it is increasing.

Supply chain financing in the logistics system refers to the financing of supply chain enterprises, as well as related services such as settlement and insurance, by commercial banks and financial institutions, especially in innovative cooperation with logistics enterprises. [1].

World experience shows that the market and competition are the main mechanisms of modern economic development, stronger and more effective than other factors. [2].

In general, the level of economic profitability of logistics enterprises is one of the main goals for logistics enterprises, like any enterprise. [3].

Logistics industry supply chain finance, as a developing financing method, provides a good solution to the capital turnover problems of all parties in the supply chain, which helps to solve the financing difficulties of logistics enterprises.

Ensuring the financial stability of logistics enterprises, the state and development of this sector ensures the implementation of important economic steps for the real sector.

As of my knowledge cutoff date, there were several issues related to financing in the logistics industry, including:

Tightening credit markets: The logistics industry is heavily reliant on credit to finance operations such as inventory management, transportation, and warehousing. However, a tightening credit market can make it more difficult for logistics companies to access the financing they need to operate effectively.

Rising costs: Logistics companies are facing rising costs, including fuel costs, labor costs, and regulatory compliance costs. These increased costs can put pressure on margins and make it more difficult for logistics companies to access financing.

Economic uncertainty: Uncertainty in the global economy can make it more difficult for logistics companies to secure financing. Lenders may be hesitant to lend money to companies operating in an uncertain economic environment, which can make it harder for logistics companies to access the funding they need.

Changing customer demands: Logistics companies are under pressure to adapt to changing customer demands, including increased demand for faster delivery times and more flexible delivery options. Meeting these demands often requires significant investment in new technology and infrastructure, which can be expensive and difficult to finance.

As of my current date, some of the key issues related to financing in the logistics industry are:

Supply chain disruptions: The COVID-19 pandemic has caused significant disruptions to global supply chains, leading to increased costs and decreased revenues for many logistics companies. This has made it more difficult for some

companies to access financing as lenders may view them as higher risk due to the uncertainties caused by the pandemic.

E-commerce growth: The rise of e-commerce has led to increased demand for logistics services, but it has also led to higher customer expectations for faster and cheaper delivery. To keep up with these demands, logistics companies are investing heavily in technology and infrastructure, which can be expensive to finance.

Sustainability concerns: There is growing pressure on logistics companies to reduce their environmental impact by adopting more sustainable practices, such as using electric vehicles and reducing packaging waste. However, these initiatives can be costly to implement and may not provide immediate returns on investment, which can make it difficult to secure financing.

Labor shortages: The logistics industry is facing a shortage of skilled workers, which can make it difficult for companies to operate efficiently and meet customer demands. This can lead to higher costs and decreased revenues, making it more challenging to access financing.

Overall, the logistics industry faces several challenges related to financing, and companies operating in this industry need to be strategic and innovative in their approach to financing in order to succeed and the logistics industry faces several challenges related to financing, and companies operating in this space need to be proactive in addressing these issues to ensure their long-term success. This may involve exploring alternative financing options, such as venture capital or crowdfunding, or working closely with lenders to develop creative financing solutions that meet the unique needs of the logistics industry.

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